

WORK EXPERIENCE: METHOD OF INTEGRATING EDUCATION

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Abstract:

This research was to study the work experience and multiple uses in teaching. It helps improvement the quality of education. Work experience is closely related to basic education. The programme of basic education involves work experience for all students in the primary and secondary school. The research method was used in this research was survey method and interview techniques. The sample of the study was purposively selected in the primary and secondary school in Kolhapur district. The finding and suggestion were mentioned in research paper.

Keywords: - Work-experience, Primary and secondary education, education, work shop, factory.

Introduction:-

A Programme to relate education to life and productivity. Work experience is an integral part of all education. We realize how difficult it is to make provision for the forward-looking type of work-experience for every students. But a beginning should be made immediately in selected schools and it should be declared objective of state policy to increase the facilities for work-experience in industry and agriculture as rapidly as possible and to make them available to schools for the education rising generation.

The need to include work-experience as an integral part of primary and secondary education is to some extent inherent in the very nature and organization of formal education. Traditionally an individual grew up in society through participation in its activities and work-experience formed the bulk of his education. While this method had several advantages, its weakness consisted in that it was not essentially dynamic and forward-looking and tended to perpetuate traditional patterns of behavior. Formal education on the other hand tended to withdraw the child temporarily from participation in community activities and to train him in an artificial environment for his anticipated future role in society.

This created a cleavage between the world of work and the world of study. This defect is particularly conspicuous in our system of education which tends to strengthen the tradition of denigrating work and alienates the students, particularly the first generation learners from their homes and communities.

The introduction of work-experience is intended to overcome, to some extent these weakness and to combine the advantage of the formal and informal systems of education. Work-experience is thus a method of integrating education with work. This is not only possible but essential in modern societies which adopt science based technology. In all traditional societies an antithesis between education and work is usually postulated, partly because the techniques of production are primitive and do not necessarily require formal education. Special skills or high intellectual ability and partly because the work is generally manual, low paid, akin drudgery and confined mostly to the uneducated lower classes.

Statement of aim :- Work Experience: Method of Integrating Education

Objectives of the study :-

1. To study the various part of the work-experience.
2. To study the work-experience and teachers co-relation.
3. To study the work-experience as a method.

Limitation of the study:-

This research is confined a primary and secondary teachers working at school level.

Research Methodology :- The method adopted for collecting a data was a survey method. The 85 structured questionnaire were formulated and distributed randomly to the selected sample.

Sample :-

The 85 teachers(Cluster Head Or Kendra Pranukh) were selected for collecting a

data.

Kolhapur District

Sr.No.	Name of Taluka	No. of Teachers (Cluster-Head)	Gender	
1	Gaganbawada	17	15	2
2	Radhanagari	11	11	0
3	Bhudargarh	7	7	0
4	Shahuwadi	11	11	0
5	Kagal	9	7	2
6	Shirol	2	2	0
7	Chandgarh	11	9	2
8	Karveer	9	6	3
9	Ajara	8	7	1

Observation: -

In all Taluka of Kolhapur district the female teacher (Cluster Head) is very poor than the male teacher (Cluster Head).

Tools: -

In this study a questionnaire was prepared by researcher and verifies the tool from expert.

Method of the study:-

This research is related to cluster- head (Kendra Pramukh) survey method is used to collect the data from cluster- head(Kendra Pramukh) those participated in service training programme arranged by DIET,Kolhapur.

Analysis and interpretation of data:-

The data were analyzed by the use of simple descriptive statistics to facilitate the data.

Activity	Response of Teachers (Cluster-Head)	% of response of (Cluster Head) Teachers
Teaching Skill- projects, Assignments.	72	88.24
Social activity (work with students)	69	81.18
Supervisory teaching	84	98.82
Group work	75	88.24
Competition & other activity	62	72.94

The above table shows that supervisory teaching is 98.82 % are most important in work experience as a integrating method of education. The group work is 88.24%,Competition and other activity is 72.94% ,social activity is 69% and teaching skill is 88.24% are the elements of work experience.

Conclusion:-

After seeing all details of data and every question covered in tools the conclusion are

- 1.The IT skill is included in work experience education and develop skill of communication.
- 2.The teacher (cluster Head) to engage them selves in productive work tends disappear because with the adoption of the new technology work at industry or on the farm becomes more productive and remunerative.
3. The cluster- head becomes an important source of production and the uneducated person, an unproductive burden on society . This process which has already started in our country needs to be accelerated and therefore the inclusion of work-experience as an integral part of all education acquires an urgent significance.

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